

TRANSVERSE MULTIPLE CRACKING OF TOWS IN WOVEN CMCs: FROM OBSERVATION TO VIRTUAL TESTING

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SUMMARY

The present paper develops the method of virtual testing to investigate the local response of tows in a textile Ceramic Matrix Composite (CMC) under various loading conditions. The transverse tows contain matrix, voids and fibres which act as stress concentrators. The mesh is constructed from micrographs of composite cross sections. Multiple cracking was simulated. Cracks were introduced into the mesh. Transverse tow tensile behavior and flaw density functions were derived from finite element computations of stress-state.

Keywords: woven CMCs, transverse damage in tows, virtual testing, FE simulation

INTRODUCTION

Damage in Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMCs) is controlled by loading conditions, the mechanical properties of elemental constituents and multiple scale structure. Because of the coexistence of very different length scales (from millimetre to microns) as well as the stochastic features of damage in terms of initiation and location, experimental studies at macroscopic scales present limitation and they do not allow microstructure/properties correlation.

The present paper proposes a virtual testing procedure which was applied to transverse cracking of the weft tows in a 2D woven SiC/SiC composite. The procedure is aimed at testing local volume elements by using as simple as possible Finite Elements simulations. Simulation cells represent different scale aspects. They can be damaged by introducing cracks in the meshes. The strength of this procedure is that crack initiation is based on constituent properties and the effect of cracks is then studied at the weft scale.

Structural characteristics of woven CMCs and damage (particularly damage in transverse tows) are first outlined. Meshing of the FE cells is described. Issues concerning mesh accuracy with respect to actual material are discussed and crack initiation and propagation are described. Then the virtual testing process will be set: several tests have been conducted. Comparison of results with the actual knowledge on damage in CMCs allows us to conclude on the relevance of this work and the improvements that can be done.

DAMAGE IN WOVEN CMCs

In this section, the multiple scale structure of woven CMCs is presented. Observations on damaged probes show that different modes of damage occur successively because of the typical structural features and mechanical properties of constituents. We will then focus on transverse damage in tows and define the guidelines for the virtual testing procedure.

Woven Ceramic Matrix Materials

The materials studied here are made of woven preforms of carbon or silicon carbide fibres infiltrated by a ceramic matrix via CVI (chemical vapour infiltration) or CVD (chemical vapour deposition) process. At the mesoscopic scale we distinguish tows and inter-tow matrix. Beyond the differences in the mechanical properties of the basic constituents, the structural configuration can be different from a composite to another in terms of amount of fibres in tows or defects distribution. Yet the tows are always structured the same way: fibres, intra-tow matrix and voids.

We can see fig.1 that the composite can be initially damaged because of the thermal stress induced by the thermo-mechanical contrast between fibres and matrix that builds up during the cooling down step after the deposition of matrix. On fig.2 numerical reconstruction of a transverse tow cut out of SiC/SiC composite shows approximately 500 fibres whereas they are more than 2300 in a tow of the C/SiC shown fig.1.

Figure 1: C/SiC 2.5D mesostructure (left) and microstructure details (right).

Figure 2: SiC/SiC transverse view of a tow.

Damage in CMCs

Progression of damage reduces composite stiffness in the loading direction. For a simple (along axes) loading case, we identify the longitudinal and transversal tows relatively to the loading direction. Three main damage modes appear successively [1]:

- **Transverse damage** in tows: in the transverse tows, matrix cracks initiated by fibres and voids propagate through the intra-tow matrix until reaching the longitudinal tows where deviation occurs along the interface with inter-tows matrix.
- **Inter-tows matrix damage**: after saturation of transverse damage the inter-tows matrix mainly situated around longitudinal tows undergoes multiple cracking. Deviation of these cracks occurs also along the interface with longitudinal tows.
- **Longitudinal damage** in tows: after saturation of previous damage, longitudinal tows carry the loads. Intra-tow matrix cracks bridging the fibres develop. Fibre breaks then lead to the failure of the tow.

The distinction between longitudinal and transverse tows must be relative to on-axis loading: for a damaged piece of material that has been 90° rotated with respect to loading direction and damaged, the former transverse tows are now the longitudinal ones and all tows are transversely and longitudinally damaged.

The illustration fig.3 on the left shows the widely opened cracks of transverse damage in the tows and around longitudinal tows the inter-tows matrix whereas the longitudinal damage in tows was not represented. On the right we clearly see matrix cracking around longitudinal tows (black arrow) and also transverse damage cracks in transverse tows (white arrow).

Figure 3: Damage process in woven CMCs (left) and SiC/SiC damage (right).

Multiple transverse cracking in tows: mechanical interpretation

Multiple cracking has been studied, characterized and modelled for micro and minicomposites [2]. They consist of composites reinforced either by single fibres or single tows. The crack network consists of cracks orthogonal to the loading direction parallel to the fibres.

Multiple cracking involves two clearly identified phenomena: statistical dispersion in matrix failure data associated to the presence of defects and reloading of surviving volume elements. In micro- and mini-composites the random distribution of matrix flaws induces statistical features and the fibres act as reinforcement that reloads the undamaged parts of matrix. Concerning the transverse damage in tows, fibres and voids

in the intra-tow matrix act as defects that concentrate the stresses and are responsible for the dispersion of matrix failure data and the longitudinal neighbouring tows are the reloading elements.

These specific effects have to be introduced explicitly in the meshes of the virtual testing process.

F.E. SIMULATION CELLS

The meshing procedure is described in this section. The calculation mesh is constructed from composite cross section. The transverse tow is extracted from the micrograph and fibres and voids are identified. The mesh accuracy and its impact on computational results are discussed. Criteria for cracks initiation are then considered as well as propagation characteristics in order to validate the crack meshing procedure.

Meshing the cells: the Heterogeneous Object Approach

The meshing procedure starts with numerical analysis of the image of a tow (fig.2). First of all, contrast smoothing is done to obtain the same colour levels per constituent. The fibres are then modelled as ellipses, centre position, minor and major axes and orientation angles of which are identified. The frontiers of voids are described using a list of points. These data are transformed into a mesh. The accuracy of the mesh around the pores was adapted to avoid irregularities in the meshed interface that would generate stress concentrations or overestimations.

We want to take into account the mesoporosity around the tow. Its frontier is thus identified as the envelop curve of the peripheral fibres dilated to the appropriate width.

The tow is then placed between two reinforcement elements which represent the longitudinal tows. They consist of an elastically equivalent material whose properties are obtained using classical mixtures law.

Figure 4: Simulation cell (left) and mesh details (right).

Cracks: failure criteria

As it is well-known for monolithic ceramic, failure of constituents in CMCs is brittle except in some cases of environmental activated delayed failure of fibres. The microstructure of the tows through transverse sections displays heaps of inclusions. Voids and fibres are regarded as inclusions with respectively a null young modulus and

a given one (E_f). They act as stress concentrators. In that way they are considered as defects responsible for crack initiation.

We consequently chose a stress criterion to describe crack initiation in the tow. Both fibres and voids populations are in competition. For each defect a post-processing operation is used to find the maximum stress along matrix interface. This stress defines the defect critical stress σ_{Cf} for a fibre and σ_{Cp} for a void.

$$\sigma_C(i) = \max_{interface(i)} (\sigma_I) \quad \text{eq.1}$$

where σ_I is the principal stress around the interface.

The failure criterion is simply expressed as:

$$\sigma_R \leq \sigma_C \quad \text{eq.2}$$

where σ_R is the failure stress.

σ_R can be taken either to be uniform for all defects or to have a statistical distribution.. This choice depends on constituent mechanical properties. For example in minicomposites, matrix flaw strength is characterised using Weibull statistics. In a first step, we can choose constant values for σ_R . Multiple cracking will result from scatter in critical stress values σ_C . In a second step we will consider scattered σ_R with a view to compare and validate multiple cracking sequences.

Cracks propagation hypothesis and meshing process

Transverse matrix cracks are orthogonal to longitudinal tows direction (fig.1-3). Because of matrix brittleness, failure leads to instantaneous crack propagation as far as the neighbouring longitudinal tows. These cracks usually deflect into debond cracks between inter-tows matrix and longitudinal tows. In our case the propagation of debond cracks cannot be correctly controlled as the meshes are not adapted to this issue. However they can be arbitrarily integrated to the meshes.

Figure 5: Example of transverse crack opening in a mesh of a weft tow.

The cracks are introduced into the meshes by duplicating selected nodes. Once the fracture inducing defect and the location of the highest critical stress are identified, the first node is selected. Crack orientation is chosen orthogonal to loading direction. Through an iterative procedure nodes along the crack are selected up to the longitudinal tow frontier. The crack can follow fibre/matrix interfaces and also pass through voids. These nodes are then duplicated and reassigned in the elements located on one side of the crack (fig. 5).

MULTIPLE CRACKING VIRTUAL TESTING

Several virtual tests of multiple cracking can be carried out: playing with loading conditions or scatter in failure criteria lead to different cracking patterns (fig. 6). The mechanical behaviours obtained during various tests have been compared to experimental strain/stress curves. A few trends in the relationships between structure and damage will also be proposed.

Figure 6: Virtual testing procedure

Loading conditions and stress state

Loading conditions are chosen to simulate uniaxial tension of longitudinal tows. Displacements are applied on the right and left sides of the cell to generate a defined strain in longitudinal direction $\bar{\epsilon}$ (fig. 7). Since the FE calculation model is linear elastic all simulations will be carried out under constant strain of 0.1%.

The elastic constants chosen for SiC/SiC tows are listed in tab.1 [3]. Longitudinal tow properties were estimated using mixtures law.

Table 1: Elastic constants for cell constituents in SiC/SiC transverse tows.

	E	ν
SiC _{Fibres}	200 GPa	0.12
SiC _{Matrix}	350 GPa	0.2
Longitudinal tow	270 GPa	0.15

Simulation shows that fibres and voids are stress concentrators (fig. 7). Further examination of stress state confirms that critical stresses are located along axes perpendicular to loading direction and that they coincide with σ_{11} (stress component parallel to loading direction).

Figure 7: σ_{11} stress field: stress concentrations (red colour and arrows).

The two defects populations are characterized by critical stress value σ_{C_f} and σ_{C_p} . Concerning the fibres, two locations can be identified: either at interface or in the matrix close to the interface. The value in the matrix is $1.177^{+0.043}_{-0.007}$ times as high as that at the interface. It is worth noting that accuracy for the interface value is limited by discontinuity of some stress values on both sides.

Figure 8: Cumulative density of critical values σ_c for fibres and voids

The plots of cumulative densities show that voids are more severe defects than fibres. SiC matrix failure strength is estimated to be around 275 ± 25 MPa. The SiC_f/SiC_m interface is generally strong. Crack opening stress has been estimated to be larger than 420MPa [4]. Thus, we can conclude from figure 8 that the void population is probably that one which generates the cracks on those composites with strong interfaces. But the situation will be different with weak interfaces. The frontier between both trends needs to be identified.

Multiple cracking process

The first virtual test was carried out considering a uniform value of SiC_m strength (275MPa). The most severe void generated the first crack under a 0.026% strain.

The first observation is that the crack generates a stress relaxation in a circular domain around it (fig.9). Stresses inside are very low and we can consider the defects as innocuous. The typical circular shape as usually considered in homogeneous media is confirmed by the analysis of stress concentration distribution. Outside the circular zone, void stress concentrations will generate other cracks (black arrows fig.9). The crack also causes a significant stress concentration in longitudinal tows as they entirely support the load (grey arrows fig.9).

Figure 9: Crack unloading zone and stress concentrations.

An iterative procedure identifies the voids that generate the successive cracks. Several saturation criteria can be defined. They are discussed later. Damage proceeds up to 0.1% strain (fig.10). The resulting stress/strain behaviour and the evolution of defect population during multiple cracking are shown by fig. 11.

Figure 10: σ_{11} stress field in the damage tow with 5 cracks at 0.1% strain.

Figure 11: Stress/strain behaviour (left) and successive defects populations (right).

Results and trends

Statistical aspect. A second virtual test has been conducted considering scatter in σ_R by using a normal distribution function ($\sigma(\sigma_R) = 275$, $\mu(\sigma_R) = 10$). 99% of σ_R values are higher than 250MPa and lower than 300MPa. When σ_R is different of 275Ma strain and stress at onset of cracking are different from above (tab.2) but initiating defects and consequently cracks locations stay the same (fig.11). The strain level for the first crack is in good agreement with the elastic limit in SiC/SiC composite structures.

Table 2: Strain dependence on failure stress dispersion

Number of crack	1	2	3	4	5
$\sigma_R = 275$ MPa	0.0261	0.0329	0.0583	0.0640	0.0930
$\sigma_R = norm(275,10)$ MPa #1	0.0263	0.0340	0.0570	0.0638	0.0942
$\sigma_R = norm(275,10)$ MPa #2	0.0264	0.0338	0.0570	0.0584	0.0923

The stability in cracking scheme can be explained by the relatively low density of crack inducing big voids. Scatter effect would be more significant in the case of a C/SiC with higher elastic contrast and weaker fibre/matrix interfaces. Fibres would initiate cracks and their population would be more dense than the voids one.

Number of cracks. Several saturation criteria can be applied to determine the maximum number of cracks. The key point is that debond cracks at longitudinal tow frontier are not taken into account and they have a predominant action on load transfers in the structure. Thus the saturation criterion probably leads to an overestimation.

Stress relaxation zones around cracks can be considered as exclusion zones for further crack initiation. We are here in the case of strong fibre/matrix interface and no debond cracks which would extend the unloading zones. So exclusion zones are just circles. In that way we overestimate the saturation crack number. Once all circles overlap the tow, we consider that transverse damage is saturated. At this stage, the minimum crack spacing distance is half tow height. Thus, we can estimate the upper number of cracks in function of tow height h and the longitudinal/transverse load transfer length L (eq. 3).

$$N_{\max} = E\left(\frac{2L}{h} + 1\right) \quad E(.) \text{ stands for integer part} \quad \text{eq.3}$$

Here N_{\max} is 6 or 5 cracks. This number is slightly larger than observations on current SiC/SiC composites. Overestimation of experimental data is reasonable.

CONCLUSION

A virtual testing procedure was proposed to investigate the behavior of heterogeneous parts selected within woven composites and applied to SiC/SiC composites. It uses finite element meshes constructed from micrographs. The meshes mimic the microstructure. The fibers and the voids are reproduced. Simulation of cracking is based on the stress-state. Cracks are introduced at the location of maximum stresses, with respect to matrix and interface strengths, which can be either constant or scattered.

The tensile behavior as well as multiple cracking was simulated for a transverse tow in a SiC/SiC composite. The crack pattern was found in agreement with current observations on SiC/SiC composites. The stress-strain curves for transverse tows as well as the flaw density were derived from simulations

The maximum number of cracks was computed when the transverse tow is strongly bonded to the longitudinal ones. Exclusion zones consist of circular domains around cracks where stresses relax. The number of cracks may be overestimated when the tows are weakly bonded. Anyway it provides a first approximation which shows the

influence of tow geometry. Further refinements will introduce the influence of tow bonding.

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